

EFFECT OF ETHYLENE-PROPYLENE POLYMER (EPP) ON THE MICROSTRUCTURE OF CLINKER-FREE BINDER

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Research into the effect of ethylene-propylene polymer (EPP) on the microstructure of a clinker-free binder containing lime, zeolite rock and gypsum rock showed that EPP regulates the porous structure of the binder and slows down carbonization in the dispersed system. As a result, the strength, density of the binder and its resistance to atmospheric influences increase.

Currently, one of the leading cement producers in the Republic of Azerbaijan is the Karadag Cement Plant, which produces Portland and pozzolanic cements in the amount of about 7 million tons. In connection with the restoration work in the areas liberated from occupation, the expected increase in the volume of construction and installation work should lead to an increase in the need for binders.

The complexity of the existing technology for the production of Portland cement and the high fuel and energy costs in production determine the search for an alternative, and this issue is relevant. The fact is that the produced cement is not used rationally. The relatively low cost and high quality of Portland cement allow it to be used in the construction of both temporary utility structures, such as cowsheds, fences, sheds, and high-rise buildings, while for non-critical objects it would be possible to use a clinker-free binder. However, it is not produced in the republic. The production of clinker-free binder is not complicated and does not require large capital investments. With an optimal ratio of the initial components, it is possible to obtain a binder of grade "100", "200" and higher, which is sufficient for the construction of many objects and even one- and two-story buildings. This binder has some disadvantages, the main one of which is high porosity. Solutions made on its basis are greedily

Fig. 1 Electron microscopic images of clinker-free binder [x2000 (1) and 6200 (2)] without the addition of EPP. The difference is that the samples without the additive have a porous texture (Fig. 1, a), while those with the additive have a dense texture (Fig. 1, b).

The main component of the studied binder, the source of activity, is a high-silica zeolite - clinoptilolite, which is formed due to the transformation of acid volcanic glass fragments. Moreover, this transformation occurs autometasomatically within each fragment in cramped conditions, and therefore clinoptilolite crystals are characterized by defects in the crystal structure - they are deformed, in places have an elongated prismatic appearance and contain large cavities with an effective pore diameter of 4.4 Å. These features of clinoptilolite give it high reactivity with respect to lime. Therefore, finely dispersed clinoptilolite absorbs lime from the solution (130-195 mg / g). In a lime solution, clinoptilolite dissolves and decomposes into acidic oxides. The resulting reactive acidic oxides react with lime, forming hydrated compounds that provide the composition with binding properties.

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THE EFFECT OF ETHYLENE-PROPYLENE POLYMER (EPP) ON THE POROUS STRUCTURE OF CLINKERLESS ADHESIVES

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As a result of electron microscopic and X-ray structural studies of the composition of a clinkerless adhesive consisting of lime zeolite rock and natural gypsum stone and this adhesive with the addition of ethylene-propylene polymer (EPP), it was determined that the EPP additive regulates the porous structure of the adhesive, weakens the process of carbonization of the dispersed system. As a result, the density, strength and resistance to atmospheric influences of the adhesive increase.